

Recognition and The Public Sphere

Introduction:

In this essay, I will look at the concept of recognition and its importance in today's society. I will examine the different approaches to this concept and its various critiques. I also want to focus on recognition in the "freedom of expression" and its relationship with recognition. Should hate speech groups be recognized and be free to express racism? Suppose recognition is a necessary principle for individual identity, self-actualization, self-esteem, justice, and sympathy toward all minorities and various group identities; then, what is the solution for those who present themselves as racist, and all sorts of anti-es and phobias groups, like neo-Nazis, anti-Semitism, homophobic, Islamophobia, etc?

Many philosophers and theorists have written about recognition, including Axel Honneth, Charles Taylor, Nancy Fraser, Habermas, etc. (Lysaker, 2013, 12). This idea is based on dialogue between different groups and identities in a situation where all parties should be recognized and have equal rights and freedom to express themselves. Recognition has become a keyword of our time and is a notion proving central to efforts to conceptualize today's struggles over identity and difference. Whether the issue is indigenous land claims or women's carework, homosexual marriage, or Muslim headscarves, moral philosophers use the term recognition to mention these issues (Frazer, 2003, 1).

Axel Honneth emphasizes recognizing social justice and recognition of different identities (Frazer, 2003, 3). Based on this, minorities must be respected by society for all their diversity and differences. The government can cause suffering to minorities by violating their rights and not recognizing them. Not only governments but also the dominant values of the majority can cause misery for minorities. It can also cause them suffering, social isolation, and social exclusion. Eventually, with this unjust violation, society will not be able to flourish and provide well-being for all its citizens. In the liberal democratic society, the aim is to recognize pluralism and defend minorities who are discriminated against and do not have a voice. The purpose of recognition is to provide justice and freedom for discriminated groups.

Habermas attaches vital importance to recognition and extends this idea to the concept of deliberative democracy (Mouffe, 1999, 3). For Habermas, disputes, misrecognition, and disagreement can be resolved through equal dialogue. A consensus can be reached so that all parties can present arguments and reasons and convince each other due to the dialogue. To participate in the public sphere is necessary to accept a set of principles that allow for mutual

understanding between the parties, like freedom and equality. Finally, I will mention the theme of freedom of speech because the issue is related to recognition and social justice.

Honneths Recognition:

It is necessary to start from the definition of recognition. Recognition is a vital human need for society to survive and not end in violence and conflict (Lysaker, 2013, 17). Honneth perceives recognition as a confirmation we achieve through bodily and verbal communication. Recognition is thus based on the mutual and social relations we trade through. Without this kind of affirmation and interaction, we cannot live a good life. Recognition is a condition for self-realization, freedom, and the establishment of justice (Lysaker, 2013, 12). Honneth emphasizes that the heart of the social is *dialogue* and understanding through language processes or intersubjectivity between people. Therefore, recognition is coupled with love, respect, and performance (Lysaker, 2013, 18).

The recognition theory is related to "identity," through which individuals realize their identity and understand their essential characteristics as human beings (Tylor, 1994, 25). The violation of recognition causes suffering and marginalization of members of society who want to have their own identities and are not willing to accept the majority and centralized identities that dominate them. Because identity always makes sense in opposition to another. In other words, identity is bifacial and two-sided (who I am and who I am not). Individuals experience violation and injustice, either because of their culture, way of life, beliefs, or even because of their ethnic backgrounds, which makes the conflicts of these marginalized groups inevitable.

According to Taylor, the violation can result in a person or group being exposed to various forms of harm; it can be about harming the person himself, relationships with other people, or belonging to groups and institutions (Lysaker, 2013, 17). If the rights and identities of certain minorities or groups, like ethnicity, religion, gender, different sexual orientation, and so forth, are not recognized. In that case, there is no other way but to fight for recognition (Lysaker, 2013, 22). The struggle for recognition, or in other words, the battle for change, can be seen in Marx's works also and many others. Unlike Karl Marx, for Tyler and Honneth, the struggle for recognition is not limited to the working class but involves all social groups that have been marginalized.

Lysaker divides this lack of recognition into two categories: *misrecognition* and *nonrecognition*. A misrecognition person holds an opportunity to be motivated to a recognition struggle (Lysaker, 2013, 30 & Ebrahimi, 2022, 3); for

example, transexual groups or some religious minorities in some countries are a type of misrecognized groups. However, nonrecognition refers to violations that make a struggle for recognition impossible (Lysaker, 2013, 39). Nonrecognition should be understood as a radical form of violation that can lead to the dehumanization and objectification of those individuals. Two examples of nonrecognition are murder and statelessness. These examples of nonrecognition result in an impossibility of the struggle for recognition, and murder can be a massacre or war crime resulting from the dehumanization and objectification of certain groups of people (Lysaker, 2013, 40-41 & Ebrahimi, 2022, 3).

He also talks about the three stages of "recognition" in the following. These three steps represent the three forms of receiving oneself. The first step of recognition will be achieved in the family (Lysaker, 2013, 23). It is important because, without this recognition, a child will suffer from a lack of self-confidence. The second essential step in recognition is based on individual "self-respect". In a society, everyone should consider themselves human beings with dignity and equality with others. The nature of this recognition is essentially legal and is crystallized in the individual's relationship with society (Lysaker, 2013, 25). It is important because, with recognition in this stage, she will become a citizen who finds moral responsibility towards her society. Realizing equality with others will cause the individual to come out of a state of passivity in the face of what is happening in the community and play a political and social role, like being active in the public sphere and could have an active role in social discussion. The third essential step in recognition is based on individual "self-esteem". (Honneth, 1996, 134). Although it is a continuation of the previous stage, this stage delicately goes beyond it. At this stage, the individual is respected not because he is a human being like all others but because she is unique with his own identity, culture, characteristics, and distinctions.

It should be noted that the three stages in which Honneth categorizes recognition are all of a conversational nature or reciprocity. In other words, they can also be considered a kind of struggle in dialogue with other subjects. So, we can say that Axel Honneth and Habermas move in the same frame of mind.

Deliberative Democracy and Recognition:

Jürgen Habermas is considered one of the most influential thinkers of the critical school. While criticizing modernity and calling it unfinished and half-finished projects, he tried to complete and correct it with reforms. His crucial idea in political thought has been processed around the concepts of "deliberative democracy" and "rational consensus" (Mouffe, 1999, 4). I

think Habermas's idea of discourse and the public sphere is vital for the struggle for recognition. Hence, the public sphere could become a place where the misrecognized individuals and groups could have the opportunity to fight for their rights and provide arguments to convince other groups. In Habermas's conceptualization, the public sphere is a spatial site where citizens' opinion- and will-formation occur through an ongoing reason-giving, critique, and disagreement (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 10).

His central thesis in this model is that political decisions in a society should be made through dialogue and consultation between free and equal citizens. So, it is crucial that every group could participate in the public sphere and can speak their mind without fear of insult and destruction. When Habermas writes about *all* citizens, all marginalized groups also must have the right to participate. By introducing the concept of public space, Habermas offers us a solution for the recognition of marginalized groups. The struggle for recognition could solve through discussion and does not necessarily need physical violence to reach recognition. For example, both homosexuals and anti-LGBT groups can sit and peacefully bring arguments and reasons for their claims in the public sphere.

The first problem will arise when a particular group of people does not have the right to participate in the public sphere. So, there is no other way for them to protest and fight in the streets for their rights or be hiddenly active as an isolated, marginalized group within themselves, like the Afro-American movement, in which they did not have tribune. Therefore, they didn't have any other way but to make practical and physical efforts and protest in the tribunes that they created for themselves and bring their voices on the streets and sometimes with violence to make their voices heard by the society.

The second problem arises when some do not tolerate hearing another and want to be accepted without opposing any reason. According to Habermas, nobody has the right to impose their opinion on another, in which case it is not acceptable. Any claims or ideas that cannot be justified by reason become illegitimate (Habermas, 2006, 5).

Another essential point for Habermas is that all groups can participate and discuss various issues in the public sphere, with the condition that they recognize the *freedom* and *equality* of others. Nevertheless, there might be a problem in his presupposition for participating. He says firstly that all *citizens* should participate in the public sphere. What about non-citizens who are not recognized like stateless people? For example, Syrian or African refugees living hardly without any citizenship and wish to have citizenship so they can work and have an everyday life? Secondly, He mentioned that every citizen should respect the freedom and equality of others so they can participate in the public sphere.

However, suppose the debate in the public sphere is the recognition of a particular marginalized group and its legalization. In that case, the precondition of the discussion is confused with the purpose and *telos* of the discussion. In other words, if all participants had recognition for each other's identity in the first place, it would not be necessary to have dialogue for recognition. Therefore, a discussion for recognition aims to reach freedom and justice for all participants. For instance, if homosexuals are willing to participate and dialogue with the anti-LGBT Christians, they want to be recognized during reasoning and participation in the discussion. Some groups do not recognize other's identities as equal to themselves; with Habermasian precondition, the dialogue between those people will never occur with this default. By this presupposition, the range of topics and groups that participate and dialogue with each other will limit to sub-topics between recognized groups, such as meeting city council members to review the district budget or similar issues, not within the scope of the recognitions struggle.¹

There are other critiques against the logocentrism thesis of Habermas, especially by post-structuralist thinkers. Is it possible to change other's minds with reason and argument? Why should we eradicate pluralism and disagreement between social groups? Are all people on one level capable of giving a reason?

These questions are very vast topics, and we cannot go through them all. Despite these problems, I agree with emphasizing reason and argument between participating because one can reduce bias and try to present arguments with minimum prejudice. Just as many non-homosexual Christians accept the reasons for recognizing Christian homosexuals, and those who are Muslim accept the reasons for Muslim feminists in support of women's rights. This acceptance is often accepted because it is rational and acceptable to common sense. It is possible to provide the argument to challenge the *statue que* and make the change for the public good for every possible issue.

In contrast to deliberative democracy, Chantal Mouffe brings an alternative model called Agonistic Pluralism. Instead of emphasizing dialogue, understanding, and consensus,

¹ I think precondition and reason for these two values (equality and freedom) for participating in the public sphere is that if a group sees themselves as superior and not equal to other groups, they will never participate with inferior groups and never give them opportunities to speak their minds and share their reason. So, all groups need to see each other as equal in order for a conversation to take place.

this model emphasizes conflict, power, and language games. She thinks every consensus exists as a temporary result of a provisional hegemony, as stabilization of power, which always entails some form of exclusion (Mouffe,1999, 13). According to Mouffe, the question is not how to reach a rational consensus without exclusion; that is indeed an impossibility. The goal of agonistic pluralism is to establish the us-them discrimination in a way that is compatible with pluralist democracy. In other words, it presupposes that "other" is no longer seen as an enemy to be destroyed but as an adversary. An adversary is a legitimate enemy, an enemy with whom we have in common a shared adhesion to the ethico-political principles of democracy. Our disagreement cannot be solved and reached a unity through deliberation and rational discussion (Mouffe,1999, 11-12). For Mouffe, modern democracy lies in the recognition and legitimation of conflict and the refusal to suppress it by imposing an authoritarian order (Mouffe,1999, 13)

As we have seen, she does not consider pluralism as a negative thing and considers the existence of these differences and contradictions as one of the characteristics of democracy. However, I do not think she has set a clear standard for how an enemy can become an adversary. Will this enmity be diminished through dialogue and reasoning? What should we do when they are two opposite groups and ideas against each other who are not recognizing the rights of each other? For instance, how can homosexuals get their freedom and justice, and at the same time, homophobic groups reach their interests? If she considers dialogue a criterion, she speaks in Habermas's intellectual paradigm.

In addition, she sees equality and freedom as one the ideals of a democratic society in which everyone should be equal and free. Mouffe believes in agonistic pluralism; there is a certain amount of consensus and principle (Mouffe,1999, 13). The question is, how did this consensus come about? If this consensus is reached by dialogue, why not other topics? One can undeniably argue which side is right in a fair trial. In a court of law, the parties' lawyers begin to present evidence and reasons, and the panel of judges can determine which party's reasons are heavier. Different between the Habermasian public sphere and a court of law is that there is no dominance or power in the public sphere, and it is the participators themselves who judge themselves.

The criticism against these postmodern thinkers can level is that their view leads to radical relativism. It finds any agreement between the parties impossible and in which it does not legitimize any principle called truth. A relativistic view can result in Nazi behaviors towards the Jews being defensible from their own point of view! Further, if it is impossible to know another, the possibility of recognition and research and knowing is closed. There must

be a window to understand each other, and only due to understanding is it possible to speak about recognition and justice. Therefore, to recognize others' rights and interests, there is no way other than sitting with each other and hearing what they have in their mind.

As a result, I think this relativistic view of Postmodern thinkers will intensify the nihilistic culture of our time. Postmodernism has helped create a cultural atmosphere where the distinction between right and wrong - good and bad - justice and injustice - rational reasoning and fallacy - liberalism and totalitarianism - absolute freedom and the illusion of freedom have disappeared. This extreme relativism is characteristic of postmodernism and critics of Habermas, which also has an internal paradox because it aims to "critique" structures. However, criticism is impossible by eliminating between right and wrong, reason and fallacy. They have a kind of self-defeating argument. From this point of view, the postmodern era is the end of the general concept of justice.

Recognition of hate speech?

What about the recognition of those who disagree with the equality of people? Groups such as neo-Nazi or racist white supremacist supporters or xenophobic groups? Do these individuals have the right to share their opinion in the public sphere without shame? Should the law be ethical? Should freedom of speech be limited to specific criteria? If the state reduces the freedom of speech of certain group members, doesn't it become a contradiction with Habermasian and Honneth approaches to recognition?

According to Lysaker and Syse, these questions exist at the intersection of law and morality. They arguably demand that we treat the two realms together in a way that does not disengage the law from morality and the idea of human dignity (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 2). However, some liberal philosophers believe that law does not necessarily have to be ethical. Svendsen claims that it is perfectly legal to be an immoral person (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 5). I believe Svendsen does not distinguish between the fact that the *law* itself is immoral and some *individuals* living their life immorally. For example, apartheid law was immoral because it harmed and discriminated against many people in society. As a result, immoral state laws are not defensible. But if one individual or group believes that blacks in South Africa are not equal to whites, one is free to have that opinion and live immorally as long they do not harm others. However, the law itself could not be against human dignity. In other words, the law should be ethical.

Here are two approaches to freedom of expression or recognition of specific groups: 1. Absolute freedom 2. Balance of harm. According to those who defend absolute freedom,

offensive statements can be relative to anyone, so they should not be restricted because the limit is unclear, and anything can hurt someone. The best way to deal with racism is to provide a moral and rational reason and argument against racism (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 5). In this view, all groups, even hate groups, should be recognized, and use the freedom of speech. Dealing with racism is also epistemological and should be discussed in the public sphere, and the way is not banning or limiting those groups or individuals. I think this view is against Habermas's theory of equality in the public sphere because, for Habermas, all who participate in the public sphere should see others as equal and consider the human dignity of others. Therefore, Habermas could not defend absolute freedom with his presupposition.

Svendsen echoes John Stuart Mill's *On Liberty*, in which Mill argues that 'there ought to exist the fullest liberty of professing and discussing' and that one should be legally allowed to express oneself regardless of how immoral one's utterances may be seen to be. Mill claims that free speech is the solution to the problem of the 'tyranny of the majority' (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 5). However, even Svendsen concedes that there are some instances in which hate speech is of such a nature that it represents a clear threat, for example, to minority groups. In such cases, Svendsen suggests, these utterances should be categorized and treated under John Stuart Mill's 'harm principle' rather than being defined as illegal (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 5).

According to these liberal thinkers, the law can only intervene if there is a clear threat. For example, if a racist wants to have a scientific debate that the IQ of a specific race is higher than another race according to genetics and survey. Although it is hated speech and pseudo-scientific racism, it can be expressed according to absolute freedom promoters; hence it is not based on the threat. So, society should recognize all groups as long they don't harm or threaten other people's rights and freedom. However, suppose a racist wants to threaten a specific group of people to eliminate them from their rights and is a direct danger to the existence of those minorities. In that case, this is not allowed according to pro-absolute freedom.

The second position is that philosophers advocate the restriction of freedom of expression. They want to create a *balance of harm*. If someone harasses another with hate speech, this harassment will be neutralized by restricting their freedom of expression. In their view, some hate speech is both immoral and illegal. Law should not allow immorality (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 2-4).

Regarding John Austin's speech act theory, it tells us that 'to speak is to act in the world and to influence, preserve, or change it in specific ways (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 7). The harm balance argument's central core is a close connection between speech and action.

Creating a complete separation between words and action is a moral disclaimer of the reality that hatred can create for people. Spreading hatred can change the life and external reality of those people. Those who defend absolute freedom take away moral responsibility from this phenomenon and ignore this fact (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 8).

Consequently, the notion of dignity plays a significant role in the balance argument (Lysaker & Syse, 2016, 8). The balance of harm argument attempts to protect human dignity. Free speech may rightly be legally restricted in cases where respect for the social standing of minority groups is harmed since their freedom of expression is effectively curtailed by hate speech. In this sense, misrecognition transferred from one group to another (to hate speakers)!

I think there is a vast space for freedom of speech. Yes, freedom of expression can be limited to very few issues that lead to social violence and violence in action. These issues are limited, such as racism, ethnic discrimination, and intimidation. However, we have considerable space for discussion on all matters, from criticizing politicians to economic, social, political, philosophical, and religious spheres. If there is a *red line*, the red line is tiny and narrow. Judith Butler has raised the question, "under what conditions does freedom of speech become the freedom to hate" (Vetlesen & Bangstad, 2011, 10). Historically, we know that the repression of Jews and other minorities has always begun with rhetoric and hate speech. If the goal of a society is to create a good life with the human dignity of all members of society, spreading hatred has the opposite effect. It leads the society to isolation, polarization, and violence. Consequently, restricting freedom of expression for a higher benefit and higher values might not contradict the principle of freedom of expression because freedom of speech is a means to a good life.

Conclusion:

Recognition is a vital human need, and it can be achieved due to dialogue and conversation between subjects to achieve principles such as equality and freedom. In the third stage of Honneth recognition, we understood that equality of human beings does not mean that they are the same in all aspects. Society should recognize the differences and have respect for diversity so that individuals can have self-esteem and be proud of their identity. Still, we must remember that human beings have common characteristics and needs, regardless of their differences. Demand for recognition and respect, the need for the right to live and freedom of choice, need for equal rights regardless of their differences. Equating people in society means giving everyone equal opportunities to participate in social life and pursue personal goals. Kant believed that every human being is an end, not a mean, and should not be turned into a

tool to achieve a specific purpose. In this view, nobody is allowed to dehumanize or objectify a certain individual and do not recognize their rights.

On the other hand, free speech debates show that not all groups can be recognized. Recognition of hate groups such neo-Nazi and White supremacists can violate the freedoms and rights of minority groups and individuals. So when it comes to recognition, it does not mean that hate speech groups calling for violence, repression of dissidents, ethnic discrimination and oppressors of religious minorities, etc., are to be recognized. However, recognizing other groups who are not dangerous to people's freedom, for instance, homosexuals, transgender people, extremely poor people, feminists etc, do not hinder others and do not harm the freedom, rights, and dignity of other human beings. Therefore, it is necessary to recognize these minorities, and everybody must realize them due to human dignity and human rights.

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